

SPATIAL AND PLANNING PRINCIPLES FOR THE DESIGN OF TEMPORARY SHELTERS

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Annotation: The article discusses the design principles of temporary shelters in earthquake-active zones such as Almaty. The importance of architectural solutions to ensure the safety of the population is emphasized. The concept of temporary shelters using innovative materials and technologies that can minimize the consequences of disasters and can be quickly deployed to protect residents is considered. [1]

Keywords: Temporary Shelters, Seismic Resilience, Architectural Design, Innovative Materials, Urban Safety, Landscape Integration, Energy Efficiency, Emergency Response

The evolution of building construction in seismically active regions is an important area of research, reflecting centuries of humanity's attempts to adapt architectural and construction solutions to ensure safety and resilience in earthquake environments. From ancient times to the present, architectural approaches have undergone significant changes dictated by the need to minimize damage from natural disasters and protect human life. The importance of this approach is confirmed by historical data on destructive earthquakes that have occurred in different parts of the world and had a significant impact on the development of construction practices. Similarly, the example of Kazakhstan shows how strong earthquakes have stimulated the development of special architectural solutions to ensure safety (Infographic 1).

Almaty, one of the largest megacities in Kazakhstan, is located in an earthquake-active zone, which imposes serious constraints on the design of the urban environment. Frequent earthquakes pose a real threat to the safety of residents and the integrity of urban infrastructure, which necessitates the development of effective architectural and landscape solutions. In conditions of constant seismic activity, design should be aimed at minimizing the consequences of possible destruction and ensuring the safety of life of the population.

Effective architectural design in earthquake-prone regions requires the integration of advanced technologies and innovative materials capable of absorbing dynamic loads. Structural flexibility becomes a key factor in reducing the risk of damage during earthquakes. At the same time, architects should develop designs based on a detailed analysis of the geological conditions of the region, which will allow them to model seismic scenarios and optimize the stability of structures. The use of engineering solutions adapted to the local landscape and tectonic activity contributes to improving the earthquake resistance of buildings. [2]

Landscape design in Almaty also plays a significant role in ensuring seismic safety. Natural barriers, such as hills and water bodies, can serve as effective shock absorbing elements that mitigate the impact of seismic waves. Green spaces not only improve the ecological condition and appearance of the city, but also strengthen the soil cover, reducing the risk of landslides and erosion, which is especially important for mountainous areas. These spaces should be functionally integrated into the urban environment, providing both aesthetic value and protection of the population from possible catastrophic consequences.

Attention should also be paid to the design of evacuation areas and safe routes. These areas should be easily accessible to all categories of the population, including people with disabilities. An effective system of marking evacuation routes and informing citizens about safe zones significantly increases the level of preparedness of the city for possible emergencies.

Ultimately, an integrated approach to the design of Almaty's urban environment under conditions of seismic activity includes architectural and landscape solutions, as well as elements of social infrastructure. This allows not only to create a more sustainable and safe city, but also to improve the quality of life of its residents, providing protection and comfort in the face of possible natural disasters.

The development of temporary shelter structures is an important part of urban adaptation strategies to natural disasters, including earthquakes and other emergencies. Modern approaches to the development of such structures involve the use of innovative materials and technologies that ensure stability and rapid deployment when needed.

The use of low mass materials (aluminum, steel, composites) reduces the load on the foundation and reduces inertial forces during shocks. Prospects in this area are related to increased functionality, mobility and adaptability of temporary shelters. The material reduces installation time and minimizes the impact on

supporting structures during seismic activity, ensuring high stability of structures. For example, the introduction of seismic-insulating supports and rubber bearings with high shock absorption reduces the effects of seismic shocks, providing reliable protection for shelter occupants.

One of the key areas of development is the introduction of modular and transformable structures that can be easily assembled and adapted to any landscape and urban conditions. This is particularly important for earthquake-prone areas where the speed of deployment and stability of structures is crucial. (Table 1)

Table 1 - Types of MAF application in the selected site of Bostandyk district

In the courtyards of the housing estate	In landscaping areas	On roads

Temporary shelters must not only be durable and reliable, but also provide comfortable temporary living conditions, including access to water, electricity and sanitation facilities. Modern temporary shelters are designed with energy efficiency in mind, including the possibility of solar energy and rainwater harvesting systems. This makes them more resilient to long-term conditions and reduces dependence on external sources of resources. Also important is the integration of digital technologies for real-time monitoring and management

of shelters. Remote monitoring systems can track conditions inside shelters, such as temperature, humidity, light, carbon dioxide levels and alarm kit status, which ensures timely response and resource management (Table 2) Thus, the development of temporary shelters as a form of urban adaptation offers new opportunities to improve safety and resilience in the face of natural disasters. [3]

Variants of design arrangement by self-tortisers			
№	Location	Construction	Name
1	 [1]	Rubber bearing with high shock absorption	
2	 [2]	Seismic isolating support	

3	<p>1 – рoстeрк; 2 – oпopa пoд кoлoннy; 3 – кoлoннa; 4 – плaтa пoд oпopой; 5 – пpeднaпpяжeнный жeлeзoбeтoнный тaж; 6 – вepxняя плaтa кoлoдцa; 7 – cлoй пecкa</p> <p>[3]</p>	Seismic insulating foundation with suspended supports	
4	<p>[4]</p>	Sand cushion under the foundation	

Conclusion

The development and design of temporary shelters in earthquake-prone areas such as Almaty is a critical task due to the high probability of natural disasters and their devastating impact on the urban environment. The spatial and planning design principles considered demonstrate the importance of an integrated approach to sustainability, safety and comfort. A major emphasis is placed on the integration of innovative materials and technologies that minimize the effects of earthquakes and increase the efficiency of structural deployment in emergency situations.

A key aspect of temporary shelter design is the use of lightweight but strong materials such as aluminum, steel, and composites. These materials not only reduce the load on the foundation, but also reduce the inertial forces generated by seismic shaking. This strategy significantly increases the stability of structures and minimizes the time required for installation. The use of seismic isolating supports and rubber bearings with high shock absorption is becoming one of the promising directions that provide additional protection to the occupants of temporary shelters from the effects of earthquakes.

Flexibility and adaptability of structures are important characteristics of modern temporary shelters. The developed modular and transformable solutions allow easy adaptation of structures to different landscape and urban conditions, which is especially important for megacities located in earthquake-active zones. The ability to rapidly deploy such structures is critical to ensure public safety and reduce emergency response time. In addition, temporary shelters must provide all necessary conditions for life activity, including access to water, electricity and sanitary facilities.

Modern approaches to the design of temporary shelters also take energy efficiency into account. The use of rainwater harvesting systems and solar energy can make shelters more autonomous and independent of external resources. The long-term sustainability of such solutions reduces the burden on urban infrastructure and provides reliable protection in long-term emergencies. The integration of digital technologies is also an important component. Monitoring systems provide real-time visibility of conditions inside shelters, including temperature, humidity, lighting and carbon dioxide levels. This facilitates better resource management and timely response to changing conditions.

Landscape design also plays a significant role in improving the seismic resilience of urban environments. Natural barriers such as hills and water bodies can serve as shock absorbing elements that mitigate the effects of seismic waves. Green spaces not only improve the appearance of the city, but also strengthen the soil cover, reducing the risk of erosion and landslides. These spaces should be harmoniously integrated into the urban environment, combining aesthetic value with a protective function. In addition, the design of evacuation zones and safe routes should take into account accessibility for all categories of the population, including people with disabilities, which significantly increases the overall level of safety.

In conclusion, it can be concluded that an integrated approach to the design of temporary shelters, combining architectural and landscape solutions with the use of advanced materials and technologies, opens new perspectives for improving the resilience of urban environments in natural disasters. The use of energy-efficient and digital monitoring systems complements this approach, ensuring not only the protection of the population, but also improving the quality of urban life in the long term.

Table-3. Temporary shelter concepts (MAF-variations)

1		Above ground			
2		On the road			

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